

A Study on Impact of ICT among Arts and Science College Students in Palayamkottai with Special Reference to Projector

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Abstract:

Information and communication technology (ICT) in education is the form of education that uses information and communications technology to hold up, enhance and optimize the delivery of information. Worldwide research has shown that ICT can lead to an enhanced students learning and improved teaching methods. One of the important general ICT tools for teaching and learning is projector. This study is a descriptive survey based study. It is mainly based on primary data and secondary data. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. This generation of students expects visual simulation and unfortunately is accountable to be impressed by the matter addressed to them. Projectors permit teaching to be further visually appealing which, in turn, can help to increase the concentration of the students. The final conclusion of this research specifies that the projector improves the students learning capacity.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Projector, Impact, Perception, Barriers.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays classrooms have distorted strongly with the initiation of new technology. Information and communication technology (ICT) in education is the form of education that uses information and communications technology to hold up, improve and optimize the delivery of information. Worldwide research has shown that ICT can lead to an enhanced students learning and improved teaching methods. One of the important general ICT tools for teaching and learning is projector. With the help of projectors in the classroom, students can easily understand the concept. All the new technology equipments are used to develop the teaching and learning process more prolonged and interactive. When teachers are digitally literate and trained to use ICT, it will lead to high order thinking skill and leave students better prepared to deal with ongoing technological changes in the society. There are 6 arts and science colleges

in Palayamkottai. This study primarily focuses on impact of learning through projectors among Arts and Science college students in Palayamkottai and also to analyze the barriers in learning through projector.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Md.RuhulAmin (2018) explain in his study that multimedia projector in classroom is very essential as well as beneficial. Through the multimedia projectors, students listening power will be high.

Li-ying_Liu (2015) explains in his study that there is no significant difference in students learning attainment between coaching through interactive projector and common data projector. In this study they developed a coding system for investigating classroom interactivity and primarily examined the effectiveness of use of projector.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To examine the student's perception towards learning through projector.
- To analyze the satisfaction level of learning while using the projector.
- To find out the barriers in learning through projector.
- To understand the impact of learning through projector.

IV. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Smart technology is recognizable terminology that is generally being used in every one's existence. Classroom education is one aspect that makes learning investigational to students. Students can listen to the lecturer through power point metaphors and participate actively. This study helps to generate a student centered, knowledge enriched and highly occupied classroom. It creates a next generation learning freedom for students and faculties.

V. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is a descriptive survey based study. It is mainly based on primary data and secondary data. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 70 respondents and 66 were collected back and 6 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 60. Simple random sampling method was adopted for selecting the respondents. The secondary data is collected through books, manuals and websites.

VI. TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The statistical tools help us to evaluate the problems under the study in a judicial manner. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method and chi square techniques are used in this study

VII. DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	36	60
	Female	24	40
Stream of education	Arts	40	67
	Science	20	33
	Below 20 years	13	22
Age	20-23 years	39	65
	Above 23 years	08	13
	Up to Rs 10000		
Family monthly income	Rs 10000 – Rs 20000	18	30
	Rs 20000 – Rs 30000	26	43
	Rs 30000 – Rs 40000	7	12
	Above Rs 40000	9	15
Hours of using projector in classroom	1 hour per day	24	40
	2 hours per day	33	55
	More than 3 hours	3	5
Purpose of using projector	Study	48	80
	Cultural	4	7
	Others	8	13
Satisfaction of respondents	Yes	52	86
	No	8	14
Learning through projector	Clearly understood	38	63
	Slightly understood	19	32
	None	3	5
Effects of using projector	Visually attractive	11	18
	Interactive	28	46
	Better understanding	21	36
Availability of projector in your college	Adequate	38	63
	Moderate	15	25
	Inadequate	7	12

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table explains that

- Majority (60%) of our respondents are male.
- Majority (67%) of our respondents are Arts students.
- Majority (65%) of our respondents belong to the age group of 20-23 years.
- Majority (43%) of our respondents have a monthly income of Rs 10000 to Rs 20000.

- Majority (55%) of our respondents say that the use projector for 2 hours per day for study purpose.
- Majority (86%) of our respondents say that they are highly satisfied while learning through projector.
- Majority (63%) of the respondents feel that they clearly understand the topic while learning through projector.
- Majority (46%) of the respondents say that the classes were very interactive while learning through projector.
- Majority of our respondents agree that they have adequate projectors in their colleges.

Table 2. Impact of Learning through Projector

Weighted average method is used to analyze impact of learning through Projector

Statement	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Total score	Avg Score	Rank
Optimum use of time	19	27	11	1	2	240	48	II
Keep us engaged	8	20	9	2	21	172	34	VII
Easily adaptable to learning	15	27	10	3	5	224	45	IV
Understand clearly	25	29	5	1	-	258	52	I
Interactive learning experience	14	20	20	3	3	219	44	V
Efficient notes taking	10	15	12	8	15	177	36	VI
Easy memorization	13	31	13	2	1	233	47	III

Source: Data collected through questionnaire
From the above table it is inferred that majority of our respondents feel that while learning through projector subjects are clearly understood, followed by optimum use of time and easy memorization.

Table 3. Barriers in Learning through Projector

Garrett ranking method is used to analyze the barriers in learning through Projector

FACTORS	SCORE	AVG. SCORE	RANK
Electricity supply	3250	54	IV
Concentrate more in taking notes	3180	53	V
Dark room is required	3616	60	III
Eye irritation	3709	62	II
Sudden breakdown	3893	65	I
Heat and proper audio system	3139	52	VI

Source: Data collected through questionnaire
dark room.

From the above table it is understood that majority of our respondents feel that major barriers in learning through projector are sudden breakdown of projector while listening, followed by eye irritation while watching for a long time and availability of the

VIII. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Ho1: There is no association between usage of projector and level of satisfaction

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	df	H ₀ accepted/rejected
Chi- square	85.44	15.507	8	Rejected

Since the calculated value (85.44) is more than the table value (15.507) the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is association between usage of projector and level of satisfaction.

Ho2: There is no association between the age and the level of satisfaction while learning through projector

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	df	H ₀ accepted/rejected
Chi- square	4.29	15.507	8	Accepted

Since the calculated value (4.29) is less than the the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no association between the age of the respondents and their level of satisfaction.

IX. SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

- While learning through projectors, it reduces the issue of taking down incorrect or irrelevant notes.
- Mostly projector is used for the purpose of learning only. It can also be used for other activities also.
- Since there is a association between the usage of projector and the level of satisfaction, the hours of learning through projector should be improved.
- The major hindrance in the usage of projector is sudden break down and power cut. This can be overcome by proper maintenance and erecting generator,

This generation of students expects visual simulation and unfortunately is accountable to be impressed by the matter addressed to them. Projectors permit teaching to be further visually appealing which, in turn, can help to increase the concentration of the students. The final conclusion of this research specifies that the projector improves the students learning capacity.

X. REFERENCES

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